

ICLC 2024 - Proposal for Live Performances

Live Performances (including audio, visual, and A/V or multimedia) will largely be sorted into one of two formats: a concert format, with seated audience; and an Algorave format, unseated and intended for dancing.

1. General Information

- **Performance Title:** Coloring Code—Live Drawing and Coding
- **Main Contact:** Ben Swift
- **Additional Performers:** LXT & Beverley Edwards
- **Performance Type:** Concert

2. Abstract

I will perform an improvised from-scratch live coding set in Extempore, so it's not possible to link to an exact version of the set. However, the videos on my vimeo page <https://vimeo.com/benswift> are indicative of the sort of set I'll intend to play, e.g. <https://vimeo.com/779496006>. For further reference I also performed a solo (musical) set at the 2020 ICLC Algorave in Limerick, although I don't have a video of that—the stream wasn't working for my set for some reason :(

3. Video and/or Audio Material

References (as per note above, the set will be improvised fresh and new for the audience in Shanghai).

Previous livecoded sets:

- <https://vimeo.com/779496006>
- <https://vimeo.com/592452477>

4. Program Note

I've spent the past 12 months (and 2 of the last 5 years) as primary carer to my three kids. From March '24 I'm heading back to work, and this improvised Extempore set will explore what it means to work—both at home and away—and my experience of heading “back to work”. This livecoded set (with me on audio and LX/Beverly on visuals) represents a chance to make new connections and re-establish old ones.

5. Artist(s) Biography

Dr. Ben Swift is an academic, educator, artist and maker of open source tools for creative computing and generative AI. He's a Senior Lecturer at the ANU School

of Cybernetics, where he leads the Cybernetic Studio: a cybernetic community that makes things out of hardware/software/people/stuff to explore cybernetic systems/ideas and their impact on the world. He is a core contributor to the Extempore live programming environment.

<https://benswift.me>